

INFLUENCE OF CRACK-WAKE DEBONDING IN CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, the effect of interfacial debonding in the wake of a crack on the stress for matrix cracking is studied for the unidirectional fiber reinforced ceramic composites. A simple shear-lag model is adopted to calculate the stress and strain fields in the fiber and matrix. A criterion for crack-wake debonding is proposed by treating the debonding process as a particular crack propagation problem. Then, by using an energy balance approach the formulation of the steady-state matrix cracking stress of an infinite fiber-bridged crack can be derived. The analytical results show that the interfacial debonding toughness and the interfacially frictional sliding have significant influences on the matrix cracking stress. The theoretical results are compared with experimental data of SiC/borosilicate composite.

KEYWORDS: Interfacial Debonding, Matrix Cracking, Ceramic Composites

INTRODUCTION

Studies both from theoretical analyses and experimental observations have indicated that interfacial properties are the key factor to develop a successful fiber reinforced brittle matrix composite. For theoretically analytical modeling, both the energy balance approach (Aveston, Cooper and Kelly (ACK)[1]; Aveston and Kelly[2]) and the fracture mechanics approach (Marshall, Cox and Evans[3]; McCartney[4]) have been used to investigate the influence of interfacial properties on the matrix cracking stress. In those analyses, the fiber/matrix interface was assumed either perfectly bonded or unbonded but susceptible to weakly frictional resistance. For the perfectly bonded composite, the fiber and matrix deform elastically above the crack plane and no relative fiber/matrix slippage occurs as the matrix crack propagates. The analytical expression of the matrix cracking stress by Aveston and Kelly[2] relates to the elastic properties and the geometrical constants of the fiber and matrix; no specific interfacial property appears in the analytical expression of matrix cracking stress. As the interface is unbonded and resisted by weak friction, extensive frictional slippage between the fiber and matrix occurs as the matrix crack propagates. The analytical results of Aveston, Cooper and Kelly[1], Marshall, Cox and Evans[3] and McCartney[4] have showed that the matrix cracking stress was closely relate to the interfacial friction stress.

Budiansky, Hutchinson and Evans (BHE)[5] have re-examined the matrix cracking problem in

a more rigorous manner. Two distinct situations of fiber-matrix interface considered in their analysis are as follows: (1) unbonded fibers but susceptible to frictional resistance which can be either high or low, and (2) weakly bonded fibers which may be debonded by the high transverse stress in front of the matrix crack-tip. In the case of large frictional resistance, no slippage occurs at the interface and BHE predicted the same result of Aveston and Kelly[2] for the perfectly bonded interface. On the other hand, if the interface is resisted by weak friction, the BHE model reduces to the ACK result. One feature of the BHE model that goes beyond the ACK models is that the BHE model provides the result to bridge between the no-slippage result of Aveston and Kelly[2] and the large-slippage result of ACK.

If the fiber is weakly bonded to the matrix, the propagation of matrix crack may cause interfacial debonding in the front of crack tip. And, the debonding process may continue in the crack-wake region due to the relative fiber/matrix displacement in the debonded region. Subsequently, the debonded interface may be either separated or resisted by frictional force depending on the transverse stress on the interface and the characteristics of interface (e.g. the interfacial roughness). The mechanics of the crack-tip interfacial debonding and its influence on the matrix cracking stress have been investigated by the BHE, which indicated that a fairly small interfacial debonding toughness (about 1/5 of matrix fracture toughness) could inhibit debonding process from the matrix crack-tip transverse stress. If the weakly bonded interface could be deboned by the transverse tensile stress in the matrix crack tip, the debonded length was assumed unchanged in the BHE model as the crack continually propagating. The possible debonding process in the crack-wake was not considered in their modeling.

Many researches (Gao, Mai and Cotterell[6], et. al.) have indicated that the interfacial debonding in the crack-wake plays an important role on the fracture behavior of fiber reinforced brittle matrix composites. However, the theoretical analysis of the effects of crack-wake interfacial debonding on matrix cracking is still lacking. The intent of this paper is to investigate the influences of the crack-wake debonding on the stress for matrix cracking. In this paper, the debonding of fiber/matrix interface in the crack-wake is treated as a particular crack propagation problem by which the interfacial debonding criterion can be derived and, subsequently, the debonding length can be determined. Then, an energy balance approach is adopted to calculate the state-steady matrix cracking stress of an infinite fiber-bridged crack. For purely frictional interfaces, the theoretical results of present analysis reduce to the ACK results. The SiC/borosilicate composite of which experimental data are already available in the literatures is used for case studies.

FIBER-MATRIX STRESS ANALYSIS

Downstream stresses

The composite with fiber volume fraction V_f is loaded by a remote uniform stress σ normal to a long crack plane, as shown in Fig. 1. The free body diagram of the unit cell in the downstream region I is illustrated in Fig. 2, where the fiber closure traction σ/V_f that causes debonding between the fiber and matrix over a distance l_d and the crack opening displacement $w(0)$. In the debonded region, the fiber/matrix interface is resisted by a constant frictional shear stress, τ_s . The Young's modulus of composite E_c can be approximated by the rule-of-mixtures

$$E_c = V_f E_f + V_m E_m \quad (1)$$

where E and V denote Young's modulus and volume fraction, respectively. The subscripts f

and m indicate, respectively, the fiber and matrix. The total axial stresses in Region I satisfy

$$V_f \sigma_f(z) + V_m \sigma_m(z) = \sigma \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_f(z)$ and $\sigma_m(z)$ denote the fiber and matrix tensile stresses. It is noted that this relationship does not readily be satisfied in region II (see Fig. 1). Therefore, a more rigorous analysis is needed to evaluate the stress/strain fields in Region II if the stress/strain field in this region needs to be considered in the modeling formulation (Chiang, Chou and Wang[7]).

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of crack-tip and crack-wake debonding

Fig. 2: A simple shear-lag model

For the bonded region ($l_d \cdot z$) in the downstream region I, the fiber, matrix and composite have the same displacements

$$\varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_m = \varepsilon_c = \frac{\sigma}{E_c} \quad (3)$$

Thus, the fiber and matrix stresses in the bonded region ($l_d \leq z$) become

$$\sigma_f^D = \frac{E_f}{E_c} \sigma \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_m^D = \frac{E_m}{E_c} \sigma \quad (5)$$

For the debonded region ($0 \leq z < l_d$) in Region I, the fiber/matrix interface is resisted by a constant frictional stress, τ_s . The force equilibrium equation of fiber in this region is given by

$$\frac{d\sigma_f}{dz} = -(2/a)\tau_s \quad (6)$$

where a is the fiber radius. The boundary condition at the crack plane $z=0$ is given by

$$\sigma_f(0) = \frac{\sigma}{V_f} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_m(0) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Solving Eqs. (2) and (6) with the boundary condition given by Eqs. (7) and (8), the fiber and matrix stresses in the debonded zone, $0 \leq z < l_d$, become

$$\sigma_f^D = \frac{\sigma}{V_f} - \frac{2\tau_s z}{a} \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_m^D = \left(\frac{V_f}{V_m} \right) \frac{2\tau_s z}{a} \quad (10)$$

Let $w_f(z)$ and $w_m(z)$ denote the fiber and matrix displacements measured from the boundary $z=0$ and set $w_f(0)=w_m(0)=0$. The stress-strain relationships of the fiber and matrix are given by

$$\frac{dw_f}{dz} = \frac{\sigma_f}{E_f} \quad (11a)$$

$$\frac{dw_m}{dz} = \frac{\sigma_m}{E_m} \quad (11b)$$

Substituting Eqs. (3-4) and (9-10) into Eqs. (11a-b), the fiber and matrix displacements in the debonded zone, $0 \leq z < l_d$, are obtained by integrating Eqs. (11a-b)

$$w_f(z) = \int_0^z \frac{\sigma_f}{E_f} dz = \int_0^z \frac{\sigma}{E_c} dz - \frac{(l_d - z)\sigma}{V_f E_f} + \frac{(l_d^2 - z^2)\tau_s}{a E_f} \quad (12)$$

$$w_m(z) = \int_{\infty}^z \frac{\sigma_m}{E_m} dz = \int_{\infty}^{l_d} \frac{\sigma}{E_c} dz - \frac{V_f(l_d^2 - z^2)\tau_s}{aV_mE_m} \quad (13)$$

Then, the relative displacement $u(z)$ between the fiber and matrix in the debonded zone, $0 \leq z < l_d$, is obtained by

$$u(z) = -[w_f(z) - w_m(z)] = \frac{(l_d - z)\sigma}{V_f E_f} - \frac{E_c(l_d^2 - z^2)\tau_s}{aV_mE_mE_f} \quad (14)$$

Upstream stresses

The upperstream region III (see Fig. 1) is so far away from the crack tip that the stress and strain fields are also uniform. Thus, the fiber and matrix have the same displacements and the fiber and matrix stresses are given by

$$\sigma_f^U = \frac{E_f}{E_c} \sigma \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_m^U = \frac{E_m}{E_c} \sigma \quad (16)$$

These stresses are the same as those of the bonded region in the downstream region I, given by Eqs. (4-5).

Interfacial Debonding Criterion

There are two different approaches to the fiber-matrix interfacial debonding problem in the crack-wake region, namely, the shear stress approach and the fracture mechanics approach. The shear stress approach is based upon a maximum shear stress criterion in which interfacial debonding occurs as the shear stress in the fiber/matrix interface reaches the shear strength of interface (Lawrence[8]; Takaku and Arridge [9]). On the other hand, the fracture mechanics approach treats interfacial debonding as a particular crack propagation problem in which interfacial debonding occurs as the strain energy release rate of interface attains the interfacial debonding toughness (Gao, Mai and Cotterell[6]; Gurney and Hunt[10]; Bowling and Groves [11]; Wells and Beaumont [12]; Stang and Shah [13]). Following the arguments of Refs. [6], [12] and [13] that the fracture mechanics approach is preferred to the shear stress approach for the interfacial debonding problem, the fracture mechanics approach is also adopted in the present analysis.

A general case of a cracked body is schematically shown in Fig. 3, in which a volume V is loaded by tractions T and τ_s , on the surfaces S_T and S_F with corresponding displacements dw and du , respectively. As the crack grows dA along the fractional surface S_F , an energy balance relation can be expressed as (Ref. [6])

$$\int_{S_T} T dw ds = 2\gamma dA + \int_{S_F} \tau_s du ds + dU \quad (17)$$

where γ is the free surface energy, $\int_{S_F} \tau_s du ds$ represents the work of friction and U is the stored strain energy of the body. For an elastic system, U is equal to

$$dU = (1/2) \int_{S_T} T dw ds - (1/2) \int_{S_F} \tau_s du ds \quad (18)$$

Substituting Eq. (18) into Eq. (17), the fracture criterion is obtained

$$2\gamma = \frac{\partial}{2\partial A} \int_{S_T} T dw ds - \frac{\partial}{2\partial A} \int_{S_F} \tau_s du ds \quad (19)$$

If the traction T consists of n concentrated forces P_1, \dots, P_n and the corresponding displacements $\Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_n$, Eq. (19), then, becomes

$$2\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{S_T} P_i \frac{\partial \Delta_i}{\partial A} - \frac{\partial}{2\partial A} \int_{S_F} \tau_s du ds \quad (20)$$

Fig. 3: Schematic showing of a general case of a crack body

For the interfacial debonding problem (see Fig. 2), the debonding process can be regarded as one crack propagating along the fiber/matrix interface. Thus, we have 2γ = the critical strain energy release rate of interface G_d , $A = 2\pi a l_d$, $ds = 2\pi a dz$ and $P_i = P = \pi a^2 \sigma / V_f$, which is the fiber force at the crack plane. In Eq. (20), $u(z)$ is given by Eq. (14) and $\Delta_i = -w_f(0)$ is given by Eq. (12). Then, the debonding criterion of Eq. (20) becomes

$$G_d = -\frac{P}{4\pi a} \frac{\partial w_f(0)}{\partial l_d} - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{l_d} \tau_s \frac{\partial u(z)}{\partial l_d} dz \quad (21)$$

Taking the derivatives of $w_f(0)$ and $u(z)$ with respect to l_d , Eq. (21) becomes

$$l_d^2 - \frac{a V_m E_m \sigma}{V_f E_c \tau_s} l_d + \frac{a V_m E_m E_f}{E_c \tau_s} \left[\left(\frac{a V_m E_m \sigma^2}{4 V_f^2 E_f E_c \tau_s} \right) - \frac{G_d}{\tau_s} \right] = 0 \quad (22)$$

The debonding length l_d is, then, given by

$$l_d = \frac{a V_m E_m \sigma}{2 V_f E_c \tau_s} - \sqrt{\frac{a V_m E_m E_f G_d}{E_c \tau_s^2}} \quad (23)$$

For the case of purely frictional interface (i. e. $G_d=0$), the debonding length l_d equals to the frictional slipping length and it is expressed as

$$l_d = \frac{aV_m E_m \sigma}{2V_f E_c \tau_s} \quad (24)$$

The expression of Eq. (24) is consistent with the length at which the fiber stress at the crack plane transfers back to the matrix in the ACK model. It also can be seen from Eq. (23), the inclusion of interface bonding will decrease the debonding length.

To initiate the crack-wake debonding process ($l_d > 0$), the interface debonding energy G_d should satisfy

$$G_d < \frac{aV_m E_m \sigma^2}{4V_f^2 E_f E_c} \quad (25)$$

Matrix Cracking Stress

The energy relationship to evaluate the steady-state matrix cracking stress is expressed as (Ref. [5])

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\frac{V_f}{E_f} (\sigma_f^U - \sigma_f^D)^2 + \frac{V_m}{E_m} (\sigma_m^U - \sigma_m^D)^2 \right] dz + \frac{1}{2\pi a^2 G_m} \int_{-\infty}^{\bar{R}} \left(\frac{a\tau_s}{r} \right)^2 2\pi r dr dz = V_m G_m + \left(\frac{4V_f l_d}{a} \right) G_d \quad (26)$$

where G_m is the critical strain energy release rate of matrix and \bar{G}_m is the matrix shear modulus. Following the ACK model, the contribution of the shear energy is neglected in the present analysis. Substituting the fiber and matrix stresses of Eqs.(9-10) and Eqs. (4-5) and the debonding length of Eq. (23) into Eq. (26), the energy balance equation leads to the form of

$$A_1(\sigma)\sigma^2 + A_2(\sigma)\sigma + A_3(\sigma) = 0 \quad (27)$$

where

$$A_1(\sigma) = \frac{V_m E_m}{V_f E_f E_c} l_d \quad (28a)$$

$$A_2(\sigma) = \frac{2\tau_s}{a E_f} l_d^2 \quad (28b)$$

$$A_3(\sigma) = \frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{\tau_s}{a} \right)^2 \left(\frac{V_f E_c}{V_m E_m E_f} \right) l_d^3 - \frac{4V_f G_d}{a} l_d - V_m G_m \quad (28c)$$

For the purely fractional interface (i. e. $G_d=0$), Eq. (27) is reduced to the ACK result and expressed as

$$\sigma_{cr} = \left(\frac{6V_f^2 \tau_s E_f E_c G_m}{a V_m E_m^2} \right)^{1/3} \quad (29)$$

When interfacial bonding is existed between the fiber and matrix interface (i. e. $G_d > 0$), the matrix cracking stress, σ_{cr} , can be obtained by using the root-finding technique to solve Eq. (27) with the requirement of Eq.(25).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ceramic composite system of SiC(SCS-6)/borosilicate is used for the theoretical study and its material properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of composite systems

	SiC/borosilicate
E_f	400Gpa
E_m	63Gpa
ν_m	0.25
a	70 μ m
K_m	0.77Mpa- \sqrt{m}
τ_s	6-8MPa

The matrix cracking stresses of SiC/borosilicate composite as a function of fiber volume fraction for different relative interfacial debonding energy, G_d/G_m , are compared with the experimental data (Barsoum, Kangutkar and Wang[14]) and plotted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Matrix cracking stresses vs. fiber volume fraction at different relative critical strain energy release rates, G_d/G_m , for SiC/borosilicate composite

The theoretical result of the ACK model for the frictional slipping interface is consistent with the case of $G_d/G_m=0$ of the present analysis. The theoretical prediction of the BHE model for the perfectly bonded interface is also shown as a dotted line in Fig. 4. The BHE result of perfectly bonded interface and the ACK result of the frictional interface are usually cited to

provide the upper and lower bounds of the matrix cracking stress predictions. In the present analysis, the upper and lower bounds of the matrix cracking stress predictions can be provided by the relative critical strain energy release rate $G_d/G_m = 0.25$ and 0. The bounds by the present analysis are shown to be narrower than the bounds provided by the BHE and ACK models. The experimental data of the SiC/borosilicate composite are well located within the bounds by the present analysis.

CONCLUSIONS

1. In this paper, the effects of the crack-wake interfacial debonding coupled with the frictional shear stress in the debonded region on the matrix cracking stress have been analyzed for the unidirectional fiber reinforced brittle matrix. It has been shown that these two interfacial properties have profound influences on the matrix cracking stresses. The newly derived expression of matrix cracking stress given by Eq. (27) includes more general properties of composite interfaces.
2. The interfacial debonding criterion used in the present analysis is based upon the fracture mechanics approach. The debonding length in the crack-wake can be predicted by this criterion; and it reduces to the slipping length of the ACK model as the interfacial bonding toughness equals to zero.
3. For the case of purely frictional interface, the matrix cracking stress of the present model reduces to the ACK result. For the maximum interfacial bonding toughness of $G_d/G_m = 0.25$, the present analysis predicts the smaller matrix cracking stress than that of the perfectly bonded interface by the BHE model.
4. The present analysis provides the narrower bounds than that usually provided by the BHE and ACK models, as illustrated in the example.

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